

A Note on Newton's Co-Efficients of Some U.P. Soil Clays in Presence of Different Chlorides in Aqueous Media

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The present paper deals with the use of Newton's cooling coefficients of different soil-clays belonging to different soil-climatic regions of Uttar Pradesh, India.

TWELVE U.P. soils viz., soils of Agra, Aligarh (semi-desert); Allahabad, Lucknow, Jhansi (arid); Jaunpur, Bareilly (semi-arid); Gorakhpur, Nainital, Dehradun (sub-humid); Tehri-garhwal, Mussorie (humid) have been collected and their clays were prepared² for the study of their Newton's cooling coefficients (N.C.C.). Homoionic NH₄-, K- and Na- soil-clays were prepared by treating with normal, ammonium, potassium and sodium chlorides respectively by usual methods¹.

The N.C.C. values were determined by Newton's cooling coefficient apparatus³. The N.C.C. values were calculated by the equation given below :

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{20}{(\theta - \theta_0)}$$

where k = Newton's cooling coefficient, t = time in minute; θ = temperature of the medium in °C and θ_0 = surrounding temperature also in 0°C.

A perusal of Table 1 clearly shows that N.C.C. of soil-clays not only depends on the dilution of salt used but also on the type of soil clays belonging to the different soil-climatic regions of U.P. The highest N.C.C. values were recorded by the soil-clays of semi-arid (with potassium chloride system) regions with all the three dilutions (i.e., 1 : 100, 2 : 100 and 4 : 100). Arid and semi-desert soil clays recorded the lowest values respectively with sodium, ammonium and potassium chloride systems so far as their N.C.C. values are concerned.

TABLE 1—HIGHEST AND LOWEST NEWTON'S COOLING COEFFICIENTS OBTAINED BY SOIL-CLAYS IN AQUEOUS MEDIA

Treatment	Soil-climatic regions	Predominant clay minerals	N.C.C. Values ($k/n \times 10^3$) min. ⁻¹		
			1 : 100	2 : 100	4 : 100
N-NaCl-system	Semi-arid	M.K.	24.17	24.06	4.100
	Arid	K.M.	24.07	23.33	23.24
N-KCl-system	Sub-humid	K.M.I.	25.57	25.31	25.74
	Semi-desert	M.I.K.	22.91	23.00	22.75
N-NH ₄ Cl-system	Semi-arid	M.K.	25.45	25.60	25.73
	Arid	K.M.	23.19	22.78	22.53

Note : M = Montmorillonite; K = Kaolinite and I = Illite.

In general, montmorillonite rich (NaCl-system) and montmorillonite + kaolinite rich-soil clays (KCl and NH₄Cl-systems) which were found in our semi-arid and sub-humid soils recorded much higher N.C.C. values than the other clay minerals rich soil clays (Table 1).

The soil-clays belonging to different soil-climatic regions and in presence of different chloride-systems which recorded the N.C.C. values nearer to or above 25.0 were said to belong to the category of a good agricultural soil that gives better crop growth and development.

References

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